

On how to bring Sunspots down to Earth

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This paper presents a very simple model that stresses the importance of information diffusion problems in order to understand the mechanisms that provoke business cycles.

It shows that it is possible to modelize “animal spirits” in a context of perfectly rational and forward-looking agents whose only source of information is their perception on the past behaviour of the economy. In the animal spirits equilibrium the economy will move from booms to recessions according to changes in the optimism of the agents. The point is that this changes in optimism look perfectly natural. They are due to what they *perceive* that was the past evolution of the economy. *They are not due to the presence of exogenous coordination devices or shocks.*

Agents use their perception of the past in order to forecast what will happen in the future. Each of them collects her information by observing the actions taken by a different sample of individuals. Consequently, the perceptions are noisy (no agent is ever sure that what she sees is what really happened) and may differ across agents. The amount of noise that agents face is in itself an endogenous variable, a product of the state of the economy.

This perceptions will act as a sunspot would, but with the particularity that their stochastic dynamic structure will be endogenous to the economy, not assumed ex-ante. Thus aggregate investment follows a dynamic stochastic structure with the stylized features of the business cycle.

The model captures the basic points of Rodríguez Mora (1996) [21]. It adds an explicit process of information acquisition, but not without a cost. We will focus on an economy with a *finite* number of agents. We will see under what circumstances it is possible to build endogenous *animal spirits*, and therefore a business cycle-type of structure for the time series of the aggregate variables. We will then try to understand the mechanisms that generate the business cycles in this context.

In the next section we will expose the model, in the second we will find the equilibria, in the third we will study its dynamics and in the fourth we will wrap up the conclusions.

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1 Set up of the model.

1.1 Utility function and idiosyncratic shocks.

In each period there are n agents. The generation born at t lives for only one period. Each individual is born with an endowment of one indivisible unit of the single good of this economy, they either invest it on market activity or use it in home production.

This is a world of short and risky lives; calling x_t^i the investment decision of individual i of generation t , and \bar{y}_t^i the average investment of other agents in period t , the utility that individual i will receive is:

$$U_t^i = \bar{y}_t^i x_t^i - (v - s_t^i) x_t^i \quad (1)$$

Where $v - s_t^i$ is a parameter that represents the opportunity cost of not investing. This opportunity cost depends on $v \in (0, 1)$, a parameter, and an idiosyncratic shock (s_t^i) that can take three possible values:

$$s_t^i = v \quad s_t^i = -1 \quad s_t^i = 0$$

Agent i invests if and only if

$$E(\bar{y}_t^i) \geq v - s_t^i \quad (2)$$

As x_t^i is either 0 or 1, \bar{y}_t belongs to the closed interval $[0, 1]$, and so:

- If $s_t^i = v$ (positive shock) then, because $\bar{y}_t^i \geq 0$, the optimal decision is $x_t^i = 1$
- If $s_t^i = -1$ (negative shock) then, because $1 \geq \bar{y}_t^i$, the optimal decision is $x_t^i = 0$
- If $s_t^i = 0$ (no shock) then the agent will invest iff

$$E(\bar{y}_t^i) \geq v \quad (3)$$

We will assume that the aggregate shock is always zero, so the shocks are distributed as an urn model without replacement. In each period exactly α agents will receive a positive shock, and exactly α a negative one. The distribution of the shocks across individuals will then be hypergeometric.

1.2 Informational structure.

All agents are born with a common prior on the *unconditional* distribution of the aggregate level of investment. That is, they know the probability that in any given period of time the aggregate has a value $\bar{y}_t \in \{0, \frac{1}{n}, \frac{2}{n}, \dots, \frac{n-1}{n}, 1\}$. This distribution will be called q . In equilibrium, to be defined below, this distribution must be the *true* unconditional distribution of the aggregate investment. Additionally agents receive private information. They observe the actions taken at period $t - 1$ by a sample of size m ($m < n$) of

individuals. They do not know the value of \bar{y}_{t-1} , but they will update their prior (q) using this sample.

For the sake of simplicity we will assume that this sample consists on m extractions *with replacement* from the pool of agents. So the sample of each individual will follow a binomial distribution with parameters m and probability \bar{y}_{t-1} .

1.3 Space of strategies

The space of strategies defined below refers only to agents with $s^i = 0$, because, as it is clear from above, all other individuals have dominant strategies. A strategy is a map from the number of individuals in an agent's sample that invested last period, w_t^i , to the set of actions $\{1,0\}$. We will explore the strategies of the type “invest iff $w \geq \bar{w}$ ”, other strategies could possibly sustain equilibria, but are probably uninteresting. The strategy is summarized in the threshold \bar{w} .

If $\bar{w} = 0$, then the strategy is “*always invest*” regardless of what you see. If $\bar{w} = m + 1$, then the strategy is “*never invest*”. If $0 < \bar{w} \leq m$, then we are allowing for herding. If a strategy of this type is an equilibrium, then individuals will herd. The more agents are observed investing the more likely it is to invest. We will concentrate in pure strategies.

1.4 Equilibrium concept

A symmetric equilibrium is a strategy \bar{w} , and a prior distribution on the aggregate q ; such that:

1. If all other individuals are playing with the strategy \bar{w} , for me it is optimal to play the same strategy, given q .
2. The prior q is the unconditional distribution of the aggregate output generated by the strategy \bar{w} .

The first condition insures optimality, while the second implies rational expectations. In essence we are looking for Perfect Bayesian Equilibria.

In this model an agent would not care about what past agents did unless this can give him some information about what contemporary players will do. She cares about $E(\bar{y}_t^i)$, and so individual i will try to estimate the probability that other individual j will invest. She will estimate $Pr(x_t^j = 1 | w_t^i, q)$, where w_t^i is the number of individuals that he observed in the last period.

We have an equilibrium if the strategy \bar{w} produces the unconditional distribution q and

$$\Pr(x_t^j = 1 | w_t^i, q) \geq v \quad \text{iff} \quad w_t^i \geq \bar{w} \quad (4)$$

That is, observing a sample where the number of agents investing is smaller than the threshold makes the expected profit of investment negative; while observing an amount larger or equal than it, makes it positive.

2 Solution to the model.

First we derive the process for aggregate output generated by a strategy \bar{w} . Then we will use simulations to see what set of strategies can generate an equilibrium. We will see then in what circumstances it is plausible to find “*animal spirits*”.

2.1 Transition matrix and unconditional distribution of y_t .

The number of agents that individual i observes investing as driven by a binomial distribution with parameters m and y_{t-1} , so the probability of observing $w_t^i = w$ is

$$\Pr(w_t^i = w \mid y_{t-1}) = \binom{m}{w} (y_{t-1})^w (1 - y_{t-1})^{m-w}, \quad (5)$$

and the probability of observing $w_t^i < \bar{w}$

$$\Pr(w_t^i < \bar{w} \mid y_{t-1}) = \sum_{w=0}^{\bar{w}-1} \Pr(w_t^i = w \mid y_{t-1}). \quad (6)$$

In appendix A it is proven that if all the agents follow the strategy \bar{w} the Markov process that drives y_t is described by a transition matrix $Q(\bar{w})$ defined exclusively by \bar{w} . $Q(\bar{w})$ is a $(n - 2\alpha + 1)$ by $(n - 2\alpha + 1)$ dimensional matrix, whose element i, j is

$$\binom{n - 2\alpha}{y_t - \alpha} (1 - \Pr(w_t^i < \bar{w} \mid y_{t-1}))^{y-\alpha} (\Pr(w_t^i < \bar{w} \mid y_{t-1}))^{n-2\alpha-(y-\alpha)} \quad (7)$$

and denotes the probability that given that $y_{t-1} = \frac{\alpha-1+j}{n}$, then $y_t = \frac{\alpha-1+i}{n}$.

This Markov process has an unique ergodic set (there are no zeros in the stochastic matrix for suitable values of \bar{w}), this ensures the existence of an unconditional distribution for the process, denoted by $q(\bar{w})$.

2.2 Updating the prior.

When agent i observes $w_t^i = w$, he will update his prior using Bayes rule:

$$q(y_{t-1} = y \mid w_t^i = w) = \frac{\Pr(w_t^i = w \mid y_t = y) \times q(y_t = y)}{\sum_{y=\frac{\alpha}{n}}^{\frac{n-\alpha}{n}} \Pr(w_t^i = w \mid y_t = y) \times q(y_t = y)} \quad (8)$$

Then the probability that he assigns to the event that other agents without a shock invest is:

$$\Pr(x_t^j = 1 \mid w_t^i) = \Pr(w_t^j \geq \bar{w} \mid w_t^i) = \sum_{y=\frac{\alpha}{n}}^{\frac{n-\alpha}{n}} \Pr(w_t^j \geq \bar{w} \mid y) \times q(y \mid w_t^i) \quad (9)$$

The number of agents that will invest is α (agents with positive shocks), plus the number of agents that have no shock and invest. This is a random variable that from i 's

point of view follows a binomial distribution with parameters $n - 2\alpha - 1$, and probability $\Pr(x_t^j = 1 \mid w_t^i)$. So given his information:

$$E(y_t^i \mid w_t^i) = \frac{\alpha + (n - 2\alpha - 1) \times \Pr(w_t^j \geq \bar{w} \mid w_t^i)}{n - 1} \quad (10)$$

They will invest iff

$$E(y_t^i \mid w_t^i) \geq v \quad \Leftrightarrow \quad \Pr(w_t^j \geq \bar{w} \mid w_t^i) \geq \frac{v(n - 1) - \alpha}{n - 1 - 2\alpha} \quad (11)$$

If $v = \frac{1}{2}$, then they will invest iff

$$\Pr(w_t^j \geq \bar{w} \mid w_t^i) \geq \frac{1}{2} \quad (12)$$

In order for \bar{w} to be an equilibrium, if $v = \frac{1}{2}$, it must be true that :

$$\forall w_t^i \in \{0, 1, \dots, \bar{w} - 1\} \rightarrow \Pr(w_t^j \geq \bar{w} \mid w_t^i) < \frac{1}{2} \quad (13)$$

and

$$\forall w_t^i \in \{\bar{w}, \bar{w} + 1, \dots, m\} \rightarrow \Pr(w_t^j \geq \bar{w} \mid w_t^i) \geq \frac{1}{2} \quad (14)$$

3 Equilibria

When v is around $\frac{1}{2}$ there are three equilibria for this game, the obvious “*never invest*” and “*always invest*” (in our nomenclature $\bar{w} = 0$ and $\bar{w} = m + 1$ respectively) and an unique herding equilibrium, that is the interesting one because it is susceptible of generating “animal spirits”.

The animal spirits equilibrium corresponds with the strategy “*invest if half or more of your sample has invested*”. This is so because this strategy generates an unconditional distribution of the aggregate that is perfectly symmetric; i.e., ex-ante the economy could be in the “good” or in the “bad” state with equal probability. If knowing this you see more than half of your sample investing, an agents posterior of being in the “good” state will be higher than the posterior of being in the “bad” one. You think then that a lot of individuals are observing samples similar to yours, with more than half of the agents investing, this will induce them to invest, and so induces you to invest. It is the belief that people are optimistic that makes you optimistic. It should then come as no surprise that in all the simulations done with $\bar{w} = \frac{m}{2} + 1$ (when this is an integer) an equilibrium is found.

There is no other equilibrium herding strategy because a small asymmetry in the strategies produces a large asymmetry in the unconditional distribution. If the strategy is biased towards investment (i.e., \bar{w} smaller than $\frac{m}{2}$) the prior is that it is extremely probable that almost everybody with no shock is investing. Even if an agent does not see a single individual investing, this is not enough to make you believe that most of

the people are seeing less than \bar{w} investors, so it is not optimal for you to follow the strategy, so it is not an equilibrium.

This can be seen using simulations. Most of the simulations presented are expressed in four graphs. The one in the NW corner represents the distribution probabilities of y_t conditional on y_{t-1} being α , $\frac{n}{2}$ and $n - \alpha$ respectively. The one in the NE corner represents the unconditional distribution of the aggregate. The one in the SW corner is a simulation obtained from the transition matrix of the process. And the one in the SE corner indicates if the strategy is an equilibrium; if it is so, the value of the function plotted ($\Pr(x_t^j = 1 \mid w_t^i)$ as a function of w_t^i) has to be bigger than 0.5 for $w \geq \bar{w}$ and smaller for the rest of the integer values.

Figure 1: Not symmetric Strategy

In figure 1 the strategy is not symmetric, the SE corner indicates that they are not an equilibrium. It can be sustained as an equilibrium only if the value of v is very high because the strategy is biased towards investment.

The equilibrium herding strategy is an equilibrium for a continuum of values of v for which

$$\Pr(x_t^j = 1 \mid \bar{w} - 1) < \frac{v(n-1) - \alpha}{n-1-2\alpha} < \Pr(x_t^j = 1 \mid \bar{w})$$

For a continuum of values of v around $\frac{1}{2}$ the strategy is an equilibrium, because the symmetric unconditional distribution implies that observing more than $\frac{m}{2}$ investors produces a posterior larger than $\frac{1}{2}$; and observing less than that, of less than $\frac{1}{2}$.

4 Idiosyncratic risk, individual uncertainty, and animal spirits

The essence of the herding equilibrium implies a notion of persistence. When people imitate their ancestors' actions the ancestors' outcome is likely to be repeated, yet volatility appears as a consequence of the noisy structure of the model. Agents are subject to a high degree of uncertainty, and this allows for misrepresentations that with the time can turn out to be true. Agents can have misconceptions about the past because the sample that they get is relatively small. The existence of idiosyncratic risk (the shocks) generates the possibility that, even if everybody without shocks is producing, a relatively large number of individuals see low levels of investment, and thus becomes pessimistic, and thus decides not to invest.

When a group of agents believe wrongly that the previous period was pretty bad they assume that most people believe what they do, and so believing that others are pessimistic, they themselves become pessimistic. The past acts as a sunspot.

The point is that after they stop investing there are more than α agents not investing and it is easier that the process is repeated; it becomes easier that a bigger set of individuals decide that bad times are ahead. In taking a decision individuals also affect the beliefs of the people observing them, and so their actions. Therefore movements from the good to the bad state (and vice versa) become an event of positive measure.

In summary, volatility arises because:

- Individuals suffer from high levels of uncertainty and can make mistakes. The level of individual uncertainty increases with the idiosyncratic risk and decreases with the sample size.
- The number of individuals that make mistakes is in itself a random variable (a consequence of the world being “small”)

There is some aggregate noise, but ex-ante it has no structure. It is the model in itself that gives a business cycles type of stochastic structure to the aggregate noise.

When the economy is “not too noisy” the unconditional probability distribution is “double-bell-shaped” with the probability of getting an average value being almost zero (see figure 2). This indicates that when the economy is in a state, good or bad, it is almost impossible to leave it. Ex-ante the economy is as likely to be in the good as in the bad state, but once it arrives to one of these states, it gets locked-in. It is very unlikely that an agent makes a mistake, and even if she does it is most likely that she will not induce other agents to make mistakes, because their sample is significantly large.

If the economy were played again and again from scratch, half of the time it would be in the good state forever, and half of the time in the bad state forever. The strategy is the same, but the outcomes are radically different in one circumstance or the other. This

Figure 2: “Not too noisy” economy. Very high persistence.

is in line with the traditional results of the herding literature; small perturbations at the beginning of the process generate strong consequences forever, the process presents strong hysteresis.

When the level of uncertainty that individuals confront increases (either because there is more idiosyncratic risk, or a smaller sample) this stops being true. The unconditional distribution is still double-bell-shaped, but now the probability of getting average values is away from zero (see figure 3).

Figure 3: Bimodal unconditional distribution

In this case the economy is literally “*jumping*” from one state to the other every so often. When it is in one state it will tend to remain there for quite a long time, but some times a cascade will be generated and the state could change. It is the relatively

high level of individual uncertainty what allows a relatively high number of mistakes to be produced every so often, and so volatility is generated. When the economy is in an extreme the individuals have a low but significant level of uncertainty, most of the time they won't make mistakes, but every so often it will happen. The closer the economy is to the center, the more likely mistakes are; the signal becomes less informative in average values because there is more or less the same number of agents investing and not investing and the probabilities that the sample tells you one thing or the other are roughly equal. The conditional distribution is flatter towards the center, the economy is more volatile and movements towards an extreme are more likely.

If we increase the level of uncertainty even further the unconditional distribution becomes single-bell-shaped (see figure 4), the economy is most of the time at an average level of investment. But we still have persistence, when y_t is below average, it will most likely be below average also at $t + 1$. When the economy is below (above) average the conditional distribution has a maximum in below (above) average values.

Figure 4: Agents facing high levels of uncertainty

A Transition Matrix

All the agents follow a given strategy \bar{w} . At $t - 1$ the aggregate was y_{t-1} , then at t it will take the value $y_t = \frac{\alpha}{n}$ if and only if all the agents without shock see $w_t^i < \bar{w}$.

There are $n - 2\alpha$ individuals without a shock, so the probability of all of them observing a number of investors smaller than the threshold is

$$\Pr(y_t = \frac{\alpha}{n} | y_{t-1}) = \binom{n - 2\alpha}{0} \left(1 - \Pr(w_t^i < \bar{w} | y_{t-1})\right)^0 \left(\Pr(w_t^i < \bar{w} | y_{t-1})\right)^{n-2\alpha} \quad (15)$$

Using the same arguments the probability that only one agent without shock observes investment above the threshold is

$$\Pr(y_t = \frac{\alpha + 1}{n} | y_{t-1}) = \binom{n - 2\alpha}{1} \left(1 - \Pr(w_t^i < \bar{w} | y_{t-1})\right)^1 \left(\Pr(w_t^i < \bar{w} | y_{t-1})\right)^{n-2\alpha-1} \quad (16)$$

And in general $\forall y \in \{\alpha, \alpha + 1, \dots, n - \alpha\}$:

$$\Pr(y_t = y \mid y_{t-1}) = \binom{n - 2\alpha}{y - \alpha} \left(1 - \Pr(w_t^i < \bar{w} \mid y_{t-1})\right)^{y - \alpha} \left(\Pr(w_t^i < \bar{w} \mid y_{t-1})\right)^{n - 2\alpha - (y - \alpha)} \quad (17)$$

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